

THE IMPACT OF ACCOUNTING POLICIES ON FINANCIAL RESULTS

IMPACTUL POLITICILOR CONTABILE ASUPRA REZULTATELOR FINANCIARE

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Abstract. *Applying appropriate accounting policies, in particular choosing alternatives to National Accounting Standards or International Financial Reporting Standards, can have a significant impact on financial results, as the entity may choose, within the law, to model or improve its financial statements.*

The analysis carried out in this article shows that there are certain aspects that can be modified to obtain an advantageous financial result for the entity, at the same time without violating the law, but only using correctly different accounting methods, for example valuation of fixed assets, income tax, amortization of fixed assets, etc.

Keyword: *financial result, accounting methods, entity, IFRS, NAS, accounting policies*

JEL: M41, F65

Introduction

Currently, accounting policies are a relevant tool in the management of the entity, so more, more attention is being paid to their design, and implementation, as it is a requirement of accounting law. They play a key role in accounting for economic facts and should be aimed at implementing the entity's strategy.

The literature includes various approaches to the concept of accounting policies related in particular to their definition, development and use. Most of these approaches examine accounting policies with a view to providing an accurate picture of financial position and performance⁴⁰. In this context, we refer to the appropriate legal methods of evaluation, recognition, calculation, etc., by applying which the results made available to internal users will be correctly presented, ensuring the coherence and stability necessary for the proper functioning of the entities and, last but not least, the integrity of heritage.

Therefore, the legal obligation of the management of each entity, regarding the elaboration and application of its own accounting policies as efficient as possible, implies the use of the contribution of professional financial accounting staff, as efficiency is, finally yet importantly, a fundamental condition of the entity's development. In our opinion, the accounting policies adapted to the specifics of the entity constitute a valuable working tool with triple application value.

First, it serves the accounting in the correct legal and interest-bearing approach to the entity's accounting operations and the presentation of accounting information in the separate financial statements.

⁴⁰ COSMULESE, C.G., HLACIUC, E., Assortments on performance of economic entities, European Journal of Accounting, Finance & Business, 2019, Vol. 10, Issue 20. <http://www.accountingmanagement.ro/index.php?pag=showcontent&issue=20&year=2019>

Secondly, the accounting policies are an element of control at the disposal of the management, with the help of which it constantly monitors, until the end of each management period, the issues related to the state of the established objectives, respecting the legality in dealing with economic facts and, finally, the timely and correct decision-making that is required.

Thirdly, it serves as a relevant tool in the audit engagement to verify the compliance of current and comprehensive accounting policies, compliance with applicable accounting principles, methods and techniques, and to assess the impact of the audited entity's applicable accounting policies on the reliability of financial statements.

Basic Content

In an uncertain and unstable economic environment, entities are "forced" to use a little creativity to survive, as each entity seeks to achieve its own goals, but these are often overshadowed by the pressures on their business. The biggest pressures, as shown in Figure 1, come from external users: the state, investors, business and social partners, bank creditors who through pressure will facilitate the use of creative techniques of the entity.

Figure 1. External users that can generate the appearance of creative accounting items

Source: developed by the authors

• Pressure from the state

The state through the control and regulatory bodies exerts the greatest pressure on the entities. The situation is also exacerbated by existing problems: unpredictable legislation and excessive taxation. In addition to the multitude of fees, taxes and contributions, the entities are often surprised by the new changes in the legislation. These problems provide the perfect excuse to manipulate accounting figures. In addition to this, accounting standards, due to their inadequacy and sometimes-even freedom of interpretation, offer options and possibilities for manipulating the information presented in the financial statements. The bottom line is that current regulations allow, at the limit, the phenomenon of creative accounting, and entities take advantage of inconsistencies in legislation to ease their tax burden.

• Investor pressure

Investors are primarily interested in the ability of entities to make future profits and gains. They encourage creative accounting practices through the overemphasis on accounting performance. It should be noted that investors are not a homogeneous group, as some investors hold ordinary shares in the entity and another part preferential shares. It is easy to understand why the first category is interested in growing the business, and the second, in the security of profit. The management of the

entity wants to pay dividends as low as possible, in this sense it can use creative accounting techniques.

• **Pressure from the business and social partners**

Unsatisfactory performance of entities affects business and social relations. Suppliers are interested in the extent to which the entity will be able to meet its financial obligations, and customers are interested in the continuity of the entity's business. Management can only benefit from these relationships. From suppliers - trade credits, from customers - loyalty. On the other hand, there is the category of employees who are interested in the performance and prospects of the entity. Their interest is to increase wages and job security. The management of the entity, as a rule, will prefer investments to the detriment of salary increases, and creative accounting techniques will influence the profit.

• **Pressure from bank creditors**

Bank creditors are interested in the institution's ability to repay loans. Creditors may shorten the repayment terms at any time if the entity's performance is not even satisfactory. In this case, the management solution is creative accounting. The management of the entity being subjected to a multilateral pressure, chooses the easiest way to achieve its pre-established objectives, that of "beautifying" the figures in the accounts.

Along with the pressure exerted by external users, there are many other motivations for entities to be tempted by creative accounting. In Table 1 are shown only some of the most common motivations for creativity, as well as their impact on the content of financial statements.

In the context of the value judgments presented so far in the present scientific approach, we would like to mention that creative accounting will exist as long as there will be options and freedoms in the provisions of the national and international conceptual accounting framework. We can juggle the result or change the appearance of the annual financial statements by using a series of techniques, options and freedoms left by the accounting texts. Experience shows that every time a new rule emerges, entities find a way to minimize its impact. Therefore, no matter how many rules the profession implements, there will always be some who will find a way to "beat" the system. As a result, the mission of normalizers and professional accountants is not a simple one: the imagination must be answered with imagination.⁴¹

Table 1. Motivations "pro" creative accounting and their impact on content of the Financial Statements

Motivations „pro” creative accounting	Explanation	The impact on content of the Financial Statements
1	2	3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Payment of lower fees 	The higher the profit, the higher the tax	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>undervalued income</i> • <i>overestimated costs and expenses</i> • <i>assets may be undervalued</i> • <i>overvalued liabilities</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New loans, obtaining advantageous rates on existing loans 	The lower the risk, the lower the interest rate charged by creditors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>minimized debts</i> • <i>overvalued assets</i> • <i>undervalued liabilities</i> • <i>overvalued income</i>

⁴¹ Feleaga N., Malciu L., Policies and accounting options (Fair accounting versus Bad accounting), Economic Publishing House, Bucharest, 2002.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obtaining bonuses 	The bonus is based on profit. The higher the profit, the higher the bonus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>overvalued income</i> • <i>underestimated costs and expenses</i> • <i>overvalued assets</i> • <i>undervalued liabilities</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimizing the share price 	When buying shares, the interest is to pay the lowest price	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>undervalued income</i> • <i>underestimated costs and expenses</i> • <i>undervalued assets</i> • <i>overvalued liabilities</i>

Source: developed by the authors.

We would like to mention that in order to achieve their objectives; managers can use three categories of creative accounting methods presented in *Figure 2*.

Figure 2. Classification of creative accounting methods

Source: elaborated by the authors.

- **Existence of several accounting options**

The freedom of choice launched by normalizers through the existence of several accounting options can influence both the financial position and the performance of the entity, as well as certain economic indicators, such as solvency and the degree of indebtedness. Example: the possibility to choose the recording of certain expenses as fixed assets, in order to then record them gradually, as depreciation in the profit and loss situation and to record these expenses in full in the profit and loss situation.

- **Estimates and forecasts**

The necessary estimates and forecasts adopted by an entity to determine the monetary values that correspond to the selected measurement bases for assets, liabilities, losses and the evolution of owners' funds may create the opportunity to manipulate values depending on the desired "optimistic" or "pessimistic" scenario. Example: Estimating the residual value of an asset can influence the calculation of depreciation expense, which affects both the income statement and the balance sheet value of the asset.

- **Use of artificial transactions**

The use of artificial transactions offers managers the opportunity to manipulate the amounts in the balance sheet or to "smooth" the result. Example: sales and lease-back operations influence, on the one hand, the recording of a current profit and the decrease in the value of the balance sheet asset, and, on the other hand, the recording of a future periodic expense with the rent of the asset, which influences the decrease of the result.

At the same time, when choosing a certain creative practice, the impact it will have on the financial situation and performance of the entity will be taken into account. Thus, creative accounting practices can be classified according to those that will have an impact on profit and loss, balance sheet and outcome measurement (*Figure 3*).

Figure 3. Creative accounting practices.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Conclusion

Concluding the above mentioned, we would like to highlight that the creative techniques for modeling the balance sheet and the information contained in the financial statements do not present any legal irregularities, because compared to accounting standards the management of the entity has a certain freedom in choosing accounting methods for transactions and economic phenomena. The issue of creative accounting includes a number of controversies, widely debated in the international literature, which mainly concern some of the stricter changes in accounting standards. At the same time, the existence of a stricter regulatory framework leads to the fact that entities find ways to minimize its impact, because no matter how many rules are not implemented, the creative accountant will always find a privileged field of action of creative accounting.

In addition, we would like to distinguish two basic points after the research was made:

1. The presence of options in accounting based on the freedom of selection and estimation or evaluation allows the management of the entity to use the creative accounting engineers to promote and support the image of the entity.
2. The balance sheet and financial statements that are prepared using creative techniques do not present any legal irregularities, because according to the accounting standards the management of the entity has a certain freedom in choosing the methods of accounting for transactions and economic phenomena.

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